

PLEA BARGAINING IN INDIA: A POSSIBLE REMEDY FOR PRISON REFORM

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Abstract: The adversarial¹ system of criminal justice is adopted in India. However, deviating from the system, the policy measures for settlement of disputes without resorting through Court room trials are provided for in respect of both civil and criminal cases. In civil cases the provisions under Section 89 Code of Civil Procedure, 1908 and the Legal Services Authorities Act, 1987 are the widely use mechanism for settlement of disputes outside the Court. Likewise, the criminal cases could also be settled without resorting to the court room trial. One such policy measure is Plea Bargaining. Under the Criminal Law (Amendment) Act, 2005 which has come into effect from July 5, 2006 plea bargaining has been introduced into the Criminal Procedure Code of 1973. It has accordingly been amended by adding Chapter XXI-A consisting of 12 Sections. The introduction of plea bargaining in the Indian Criminal justice system was the need for remedial legislative measures for reducing delay in disposal of cases and appeals, alleviating the sufferings of under trial prisoners and also reducing pending cases. With the passing of the New Criminal Laws which came into effective from 1st July, 2024 it is contained under Chapter-XXIII, Section 289 – 300. Under the criminal justice system, the primary function of Prison is confinement of offenders. By confining the offenders, the society feel safe forming the idea that offenders have been put away far away from the society. Internationally, it becomes a well-accepted rule that the correctional mechanism in criminal justice administration should comply

¹ In an adversary system, as the name suggests, the trial is envisaged as a contest between the two parties (the prosecution, representing the victim, and the defence representing the accused) who strive to establish their version of facts as the truth with the help of evidence.

with reformatory policies². Prison administration is an important component of criminal justice system, which mainly focuses on correctional services that can change and reform the convicts so that they can live in the normal society³. The paper is an attempt to examine the concept of plea bargaining in India and the possible remedy for prison reform.

Key words: Plea bargaining, pending cases, speedy disposal, prison reform.

INTRODUCTION:

The inordinate delay in disposal of cases makes the criminal justice system weak and meek. The judiciary is regarded as the guardian of the people, but due to the delay in disposal of cases, people have lost faith upon the system. Prolonged pre-trial and back log in criminal cases resulting in delay disposal of cases had greatly affected the credibility and reliability of the judiciary which is the corner stone of legal system. Justice is something which every person on earth desired. There is a saying “*Justice delayed is Justice denied*” so it a matter of concern how many people actually get justice and justice in due time. The provision of Plea bargaining has been introduced to as an alternative measures for speedy disposal of pending criminal cases and to reduce the burden of Courts. The Law Commission in its 142nd Report had given a detailed outlined on the application of plea bargaining in India⁴. The Law Commission in its 154th Report also reiterated the need for introduction of plea bargaining⁵. The 177th Law Commission Report also suggested for the early introduction of Plea Bargaining as suggested by the 142nd & 154th Report⁶. This recommendation was supported by Dr. Justice Malimath Committee. The Code of Criminal Procedure has accordingly been amended by adding Chapter XXI-A consisting of 12 Sections which came into forced w.e.f. 5th July, 2006. With the passing of the New Criminal Laws which came into effective from 1st July, 2024 it is contained under Chapter- XXIII, Section 289 – 300.

² International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights, 1966, Art. 10 (3) mandates that the essential feature of correctional system should be reformation and rehabilitation of Prisoners.

³ National Crime Records Bureau, Prison Statistics of India, available at: <https://ncrb.gov.in/en/Crime-in-India-2021> (last visited August 23, 2024).

⁴ Available at https://lawcommissionofindia.nic.in/report_twelfth/ (last visited on August 20, 2024)

⁵ Available at https://lawcommissionofindia.nic.in/report_fourteenth/ (last visited on August 20, 2024)

⁶ Available at https://lawcommissionofindia.nic.in/report_sixteenth/ (last visited on August 20, 2024)

DEFINITION:

Plea Bargaining is a concept that originated in the United States and it has evolved over the ages to become a prominent feature of American Criminal Justice system⁷. It may be defined as a pre-trial negotiation or an agreement between the accused and the victim with the assistance of their Advocate and the Court in which the accused honestly admitted his guilt and seek for a lesser punishment. A “plea bargaining” is a practice whereby the accused foregoes his right to plead not guilty and demand a full trial and instead uses a right to bargain for a benefit. This benefit is usually related to the charge or sentence. In other words, plea bargaining means the accused's plea of guilty has been bargained for and some consideration has been received for it⁸. As reported in Law Commission of India (142th), plea bargaining, in its most traditional and general sense, refers to pre-trial negotiations between the defendant, usually conducted by the counsel and prosecution, during which the defendant agrees to plead guilty in exchange for certain concession by the prosecutor⁹.

JUDICIARY ON PLEA BARGAINING:

The Indian Judiciary has been reluctant towards applying the concept of Plea Bargaining prior to the 2005 Amendment. The first case wherein Plea Bargaining was considered by the Judiciary was *Mandalal Ramachander Daga v. State of Maharashtra*¹⁰ in which it was observed;

“It is very wrong for courts to enter into a bargain with the accused by which money is recovered for the complainant through their agency. Offences should be tried and punished according to the guilt of the accused, and if any leniency is to be shown in the sentence it should be on the facts of the case. The High Court should not have agreed to consider the question of sentence and the offer of the accused in this Court could not also be accepted”.

*Murlidhar Meghraj Loya v. State of Maharashtra*¹¹ the question of plea bargaining was considered by Court and observed “*These advance arrangements please everyone except the distant victim, the silent society. The prosecutor is relieved of the long process of proof, legal*

⁷ Wanna make a deal ? The introduction of Plea Bargaining in India by Sulabh Rewari & Tanya Aggarwal (2006) 2 SCC (Cri) J -12.

⁸ Ferguson & Roberts: Plea bargaining Directions for Canadian Reforms 52 Can Bar Re 497 (1974), at The Indian Police Journal Vol. LVI-No. 2, April-June,(2009).

⁹ R.V. Kelkar, Criminal Procedure Code 396 (5th edn., 2011).

¹⁰ AIR 1968 SC 1267

¹¹ (1976) 3 SCC 684

technicalities and long arguments, punctuated by revisional excursions to higher courts, the court sighs relief that its ordeal, surrounded by a crowd of papers and persons, is avoided by one case less and the accused is happy that even if legalistic battles might have held out some astrological hope of abstract acquittal in the expensive hierarchy of the justice-system he is free early in the day to pursue his old profession. It is idle to speculate on the virtue of negotiated settlements of criminal cases, as obtains in the United States but in our jurisdiction, especially in the area of dangerous economic crimes and food offences, this practice intrudes on society's interest by opposing society's decision expressed through predetermined legislative fixation of minimum sentences and by subtly subverting the mandate of the law".

In *Kachhia Patel Shantilal Koderlal v. State of Gujarat and another*¹² the Court held that practice of plea bargaining is unconstitutional, illegal and would tend to encourage corruption, collusion and pollute the pure fount of justice.

In *Ganeshmal Jashraj v. Govt. Of Gujarat & Anr*¹³ it was observed when there is an admission of guilt made by the accused as a result of "plea bargaining" or otherwise, the evaluation of the evidence by the Court is likely to become a little superficial and perfunctory and the Court may be disposed to refer to the evidence not critically with a view to assessing its credibility, but mechanically as a matter of formality in support of the admission of guilt. The entire approach of the Court to the assessment of the evidence would be likely to be different when there is an admission of guilt by the accused.

In the case of *Kasambhai Ardul Rehmanbhai v. State Of Gujarat & Anr*¹⁴ it was held, it would be contrary to public policy to allow a conviction to be recorded against an accused by inducing him to confess to a plea of guilty on an allurement being held out to him that if he enters a plea of guilty, he will be let off very lightly. Such a procedure would be clearly unreasonable, unfair and unjust and would be violative of Article 21 of the Constitution. It would have the effect of polluting the pure fount of justice because it might induce an innocent accused to plead guilty to suffer a light and inconsequential punishment rather than go through a long and arduous criminal trial. The judge also might be likely to be deflected from the path of duty to do justice and he might either convict an innocent accused by accepting the plea of guilty or let of a guilty accused with a light sentence, thus, subverting the process of law and frustrating

¹² (1980) 3 SCC 120

¹³ 1980 AIR 264

¹⁴ 1980 AIR 854

the social objective and purpose of the anti-adulteration statute. This practice would also tend to encourage corruption and collusion and as a direct consequence, contribute to the lowering of the standard of justice.

*Thippaswamy v. State of Karnataka*¹⁵ in this case the accused was convicted based on his plea guilty but the Supreme Court set aside the conviction and remand the case to the trial Court and allowed the accused to defend himself if he wishes and if found guilty proper sentences can be passed against him and if found not guilty he may be acquitted. The further observed that it would be clearly violative of Article 21 of the Constitution to induce or lead an accused to plead guilty under a promise or assurance that he would be let off lightly and then in appeal or revision, to enhance the sentence.

*State of Uttar Pradesh v. Chandrika*¹⁶ the Supreme Court expressed its opinion that conviction of the accused based on his plea of guilt entered by him as a result of plea bargaining must be held to be unconstitutional and illegal. Mere acceptance or admission of the guilt should not be a ground for reduction of sentence. Nor can the accused bargain with the Court that as he is pleading guilty sentence be reduced.

*Vipul v. The State Of Uttar Pradesh*¹⁷ Special Leave to Appeal (Crl) No (s). 3114 of 2022 dated 08.04.2022 the Supreme Court while dealing with delay in disposal of case has observed that though plea bargaining has been introduced in the provisions of CrPC, somehow it has not worked because the social stigma of conviction may be preventing the accused from accepting the bail and accepting a plea-bargaining position. In fact, we do not even know in how many cases is the availability of the plea bargain remedy put to the accused and would like to say that the Trial Courts must use this provision usefully. Additionally, it reduces the burden of the court, the State, the victim, and the accused facing agonizing litigation, while serving the cause of justice.

The Judiciary was reluctant to apply this principle before the introduction of Plea Bargaining in the 2005 amendment, but now with the introduction of this principle it has found

¹⁵ (1983) 1 SCC 194

¹⁶ 2000 Cr.L.J. 384(386)

¹⁷ Available at

[https://indiankanoon.org/doc/77984354/#:~:text=\(Arising%20out%20of%20impugned%20final,THE%20IMPUGNED%20JUDGMENT%20IA%20No.](https://indiankanoon.org/doc/77984354/#:~:text=(Arising%20out%20of%20impugned%20final,THE%20IMPUGNED%20JUDGMENT%20IA%20No.) (Last visited on August 24, 2024).

recognition in the Indian Court. The Court is left with no option because its duty is to interpret and apply the law.

ANALYSIS OF PLEA BARGAINING: CHAPTER XXII OF BNSS (SECTION 289 – 300)

Applicability: Section 289 - The provisions of Plea Bargaining is applicable in respect of offences not punishable with death, imprisonment for life or imprisonment for a term not exceeding 7 years. It is applicable with respect to an offence where the punishment provided for is up to 7 years of imprisonment.

Exception: Offences punishable up to 7 years will not attract the provision if the offence affects the socio-economic conditions of the country or committed against a women or child below 14 years of age.

The Central Government by notification, determine the offences under the law for the time being in force which shall be the offences affecting the socio-economic condition of the country, namely -

- (i) Dowry Prohibition Act, 1961
- (ii) The Commission of Sati Prevention Act, 1987.
- (iii) The Indecent Representation of Women (Prohibition) Act, 1986
- (iv) The Immoral Traffic (Prevention) Act, 1956
- (v) The Protection of Women from Domestic Violence Act, 2005.
- (vi) The Infant Milk Substitutes, Feeding Bottles and Infant Foods (Regulation of Production, Supply and Distribution) Act, 1992.
- (vii) Provisions of Fruit Products Order, 1955 (issued under the Essential Services Commodities Act, 1955).
- (viii) Provisions of Meat Food Products Orders, 1973 (issued under the Essential Services Commodities Act, 1955).
- (ix) Offences with respect to animals that find place in Schedule I and Part II of the Schedule II as well as offences related to altering of boundaries of protected areas under Wildlife (Protection) Act, 1972.
- (x) The Scheduled Castes and Scheduled Tribes (Prevention of Atrocities) Act, 1989.

- (xi) Offences mentioned in the Protection of Civil Rights Act, 1955.
- (xii) Offences listed in Section 23 to 28 of the Juvenile Justice (Care and Protection Act of Children) Act, 2000.
- (xiii) The Army Act, 1950.
- (xiv) The Air Force Act, 1950.
- (xv) The Navy Act, 1957.
- (xvi) Offences specified in Section 59 to 81 and 83 of the Delhi Metro Railway (Operation and Maintenance Act), 2002
- (xvii) The Explosive Act, 1884.
- (xviii) Offences specified in Section 11 to 18 of the Cable Television Networks (Regulation) Act, 1995.
- (xix) The Cinematograph Act, 1952.

THE PROCEDURE: SECTION 290

Person accused of an offence pending trial within a period of thirty days from the date of framing of charge may file an application, containing a brief description of the case including the offence to which he is charge and the application will be accompanied by an Affidavit stating therein that:

- The application is voluntarily preferred by him.
- He understands the nature and punishment provided for the offence.
- He has not been previously convicted in respect of the same offence.

On receiving the application, the Court shall issue notice to Public Prosecutor or the Complainant and the accused to appear on the date fixed before the Court. When appeared, the Court shall examine the accused in camera without the presence of the other party to satisfy itself that the accused has filed the application voluntarily. It is the duty of the Court to ascertain whether the accused voluntarily make the application. The principle underlying the Indian criminal jurisprudence is that no one can be compelled to be witness against himself. It is therefore essential in plea bargaining that voluntariness of the accused is utmost importance.

If the Court is satisfied that the application is made voluntarily, it shall give time to the Public Prosecutor or the Complainant to work out mutually satisfactory disposition which

includes giving to the victim compensation by the accused or other expenses and fix time for further hearing of the case. If however, the Court is not satisfied that the application is made voluntarily or came to know that the accused has been previously convicted in the same offence, it will end the proceeding and the case will proceed further as if no application of plea bargaining from the stage the application has been filed.

GUIDELINES FOR MUTUALLY SATISFACTORY DISPOSITION:

Section 291 - In a case instituted on a police report, the court shall issue notice to the public prosecutor concerned, investigating officer of the case and the victim of the case and the accused to participate in the meeting to work out a satisfactory disposition of the case. In a complaint case, the Court shall issue notice to the accused and the victim of the case. In the process it is the duty of the Court to ensure that the entire process is completed voluntarily by all the parties. The victim or accused if so desires, may participate in the meeting with the pleader engage in the case.

Section 292 – deals with preparation of report by the Court on arrival or failure of mutually satisfactory disposition. If satisfactory disposition has been worked out, the Court shall prepare a report of such disposition which shall be signed by the presiding officer of the Court and all other persons who participated in the meeting. However, if no such disposition has been worked out, the Court shall record such observation and proceed further as if no application of plea bargaining from the stage the application has been filed with the provisions of this Code from the stage the application has been filed.

DISPOSAL OF CASES – SECTION 293

If satisfactory disposition of the case has been work out the Court can disposed of the case in the following manner-

1. Award compensation to victim as agreed by the parties in disposition and will hear the parties hear the parties on the quantum of the punishment, releasing of the accused on probation of good conduct or after admonition under Section 360 or for dealing with the accused under the provisions of the Probation of Offender Act, 1958 (20 of 1958) or any other law for the time being in force

2. After hearing the parties, if the Court is of the view that Section 360 or the provisions of the Probation of Offenders Act, 1958 (20 of 1958) or any other law for the time being in force are attracted in the case of the accused, it may release the accused on probation or provide the benefit of any such law.
3. After hearing the parties, if the Court finds that minimum punishment has been provided under the law for the offence committed by the accused, it may sentence the accused to half of such minimum punishment. If the accused is first time offender and has not been convicted previously, the Court may sentence the accused to one-fourth of such minimum sentences.
4. In case after hearing the parties, if the Court finds that the offence committed by the accused is not covered under the benefit provided under Section 360 or the Probation of Offender Act, 1958 (20 of 1958) or any other law for the time being in force then, it may sentence the accused to one-sixth of the punishment provided or extendable, as the case may be, for such offence.

Section 295 provides that Appeal is not applicable (Except Special Leave to Appeal under Article 136 and writ petition under Article 226 and 277 of the Indian Constitution) where Judgment is delivered on the basis of Plea Bargaining.

Section 299 provides that the statements or facts stated by the accused in the application shall not be used for any other purpose. This section provides protection to the accused, if no mutual satisfactory disposition is worked out and if the case needs to be proceeded further from the stage the application has been filed. If no protection is given to the accused, there is a possibility that the prosecution use the statement made by the accused for giving evidence against him.

PRISON REFORMS THROUGH PLEA BARGAINING:

The very inception of the idea of prison reform can be attributed to two factors – recidivism and the prison system’s failure of effectively rehabilitating prisoners¹⁸. Prison in India and their administration is State subject covered by item 4 under the State List in the 7th Scheduled of the Constitution of India. The management and administration of prisons falls exclusively in the

¹⁸ P. O’Brien, *The Prison on Continent: Europe 1865-1965* in History of Prisons: The practice of punishment in western society (N. Morris, et.al., eds. 1995).

domain of the State Government and is governed by the Prison Manuals of the respective State governments. Thus, State has the primary role, responsibility and authority to change the current prison laws, rules and regulation. In the past, society have not contemplated the idea of reformation and rehabilitation of offenders, they believe that giving harsh punishment will deter the criminals as well as others to commit crime. The human society has progressed from the age old theory of retaliation – an eye for an eye; a tooth for a tooth, with the advancement of civilization crime is no longer considered as an offense against the individual but against the whole society and state took upon itself to punish the offenders¹⁹. However there were little efforts for reformation and the British Colonial Rule in India marked the beginning of penal reform in our country. In India, various committees were set up to look into the functioning of prison administration and its reforms. The Prison Act, 1894 which is the first legislation regarding prison regulation in India is largely based on deterrence principle without any reformatory-oriented or based on correctional penological thinking. The first ever comprehensive study was launched with appointment of All India Jail Committee 1919-20. It is indeed a major landmark in the history of prison reform in India and is appropriately called the cornerstone of modern prison reform in the country. For the first time in the history of prison administration reformatory and rehabilitation of offenders were identified as one of the objective of the prison administration.

Although the reformatory measure have been adopted the present conditions of Indians prisons are not satisfactory. The Indian Prison suffers from various defects, overcrowding is one of the major issues. The actual capacity of prisons has increased from 4,25,609 in 2021 to 4,36,266 in 2022 (as on 31st December of each year), having increased by 2.5%. Number of prisoners lodged in various jails has increased from 5,54,034 in 2021 to 5,73,220 in 2022 (as on 31st December of each year), having increased by 3.5% during the period²⁰. The number of under- trial prisoners has increased from 4,27,165 in 2021 to 4,34,302 in 2022 (as on 31st December of each year), having increased by 1.7% during this period²¹. As can be seen, more than 70 % of the prison

¹⁹ Ashish Jain and Akanksha Singh, “Victim-oriented Criminal Justice System: Need of the hour” 44 (3) *Indian Bar Review* 126 (2017).

²⁰ Available at

<https://www.ncrb.gov.in/uploads/nationalcrimerecordsbureau/custom/psiyarwise2022/1701613297PSI2022ason01122023.pdf> last visited on August 24, 2024

²¹ *Ibid*

populations are under-trial. Overcrowding has assumed the proportions of a major problem for the Correctional Administration that gives birth to a number of other problems relating to health care, food, clothing and poor living conditions²². Not only that it makes segregation of prisoners difficult, as a result hardened criminals got mix with first time offenders. Now a days the existence of prison is not only sufficient, the present day penology center around imprisonment as measure rehabilitation of offenders, the prison are no more mere detention houses for the offender but they seek to reform them for future life. When our Prison system is over-burden with a number of defects, the question is will the idea of reformation, rehabilitation and re-integration into society could effectively be achieved inside Jail. The idea of alternatives to imprisonment has assumed significance, one such measure is Plea bargaining, the very concept of Plea bargaining implies that the accused admit to his guilt and responsibility for his conduct. It provides a quick justice to the victim, a more victim oriented system, quick decision to the accused to start a fresh life without loss of time. In a number of cases the Supreme Court recognized that right to speedy trial is implicit in the spectrum of Article 21 of the Constitution. In *Hussainara Khatoon v. State of Bihar*²³ the Supreme Court held that speedy trial is fundamental right implicit by virtue of Article 21 and observed “*The State cannot avoid its constitutional obligation to provide speedy trial to the accused by pleading financial or administrative inability. The State is under a constitutional mandate to ensure speedy trial and whatever is necessary for this purpose has to be done by the State. It is also the constitutional obligation of this Court, as the guardian of the fundamental rights of the people as a sentinel on the qui-vive, to enforce the fundamental right of the accused to speedy trial by issuing the necessary directions to the State which may include taking of positive action, such as augmenting and strengthening the investigative machinery, setting up new courts, building new court houses, appointment of additional judges and other measures calculated to ensure speedy trial*”. By working out mutually satisfactory disposition, there is level of understanding between the victim and the accused. The effects of Plea bargaining on the accused involve receiving lighter sentence, giving compensation to the victims, early release from jail, economic saving for the states. It can also create rehabilitative and reformative attitudes towards the accused, as he feels cleansed of the feeling of guilt.

²² Report: All India Jail Manual Committee, 1957-9, Para 38.

²³ AIR 1979 SC 1369

CONCLUSION:

Plea bargaining is available in some offences, therefore, applying this principle would help the Court in reducing their work load, relieving Judges from writing detailed judgment, reduced over-crowding in Jail. The main objective behind the introduction of Plea Bargaining in India as reported by the Committee on Reforms of Criminal Justice System, 2003 is an alternative remedy for speedy disposal of pending cases and expediting the criminal justice delivery system. Despite the introduction of the system the actual use is relatively low in India. A great responsibility is posted upon the Bar and Bench to keep the spirit of plea bargaining alive. The foundation of criminal justice system in India is the requirement of proof beyond reasonable doubt to convict the accused. Plea bargaining negate such requirement, therefore, it can result in convicting an innocent person. To conclude, Plea bargaining added a new dimension in the realm of judicial reforms. As mentioned earlier more than 70 % of prison population are under-trial, therefore, if Plea bargaining is use wisely, it would reduced backlog of criminal cases and reduced overcrowding in Prison which is one of the major hurdle in achieving Prison reforms in India.